

THE PEDAGOGICAL VALUE OF RECYCLING LANGUAGE.

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Annotation: In this article, I will write about the pedagogical value of recycling language. It helps the student to expand the scope of using something new. Recycling is an important part of the consolidation of learning. It is often included in course and course book structures. Teachers can look for opportunities to recycle new language through varying the skills work a class meets.

Key words: recycling, , consolidation of learning, recycling lexical elements, PPP model, interchanged, long-term.

First of all, I want to write what recycling language is. Recycling is practising language that learners have seen previously. The recycled language will be re-introduced in a different context, or through a different skill. This helps the student extend their range of use of the new item. Now I will write the importance of recycling language. One area I was keen to emphasise was the importance of recycling language, both with a lesson or sequence of lessons. With the recognised importance of "spaced" or "distributed" learning, there is barely any need to justify recycling vocabulary, grammar, phonology and learning strategies, but there is a danger that it gets neglected, especially in view of the poor timetabling arrangements which exist in many schools which mean you may only see your classes as little as once or twice a week. In our opinion the best way of building in recycling opportunities within lessons is by using the same language in different, varied activities. Within the PPP model (Presentation – Practice - Production) this is easy, as you provide examples of new language through listening or reading, practise

them though controlled oral and written exercises then further recycle them in free writing, for example as a homework task. You can return to the same language, and maybe a bit more, in a subsequent lesson, either re-using similar activities (because familiarity is important to students) or with new ones (because students also enjoy variety). Below are a range of tasks which could be used within a single lesson or lesson sequence when presenting and practising the past tense. Each task might take only a few minutes. You will note how the same language is recycled multiple times, even though the precise activity changes. Every repetition gives the students' brains more chance to form long term memories of sounds, vocabulary and structures which can form the basis of independent use at a later time. Listening to teacher while watching a sequence of pictures (or flashcards) depicting activities (e.g. I played tennis, I watched a movie, I listened to music, I sang a song). Repeating the same language while watching the pictures. Hiding the picture while students guess what it was, re-using the language already heard. Revealing the written version of the language used. Having the whole class read it aloud together.

From my own classroom teaching experience, I've drawn the same conclusion about the connection between grammar and speaking. That is, to improve competence in grammar we need to provide meaning-based communicative activities that require learners to produce the language.

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presenting and practising the past (preterite) tense. Each task might take only a few minutes. We will note how the same language is recycled multiple times, even though the precise activity changes. Every repetition gives the students' brains more chance to form long term memories of sounds, vocabulary and structures which can form the basis of independent use at a later time.

Listening to teacher while watching a sequence of pictures (or flashcards) depicting activities. Repeating the same language while watching the pictures. Hiding the picture while students guess what it was, re-using the language already heard. Revealing the written version of the language used. Having the whole class read it aloud together. Putting the whole sequence together and reading it aloud. Hiding the language, then the teacher reads aloud the sequence with gaps for the students to complete orally or in writing. Revealing the written version once more and giving false statements about it for students to correct. Asking questions about the sequence in L2. Hiding the language and dictating phrases for students to write on paper or mini-whiteboards. Revealing the text and asking students to try to explain in L1. Then give students some new verbs which follow the same pattern and ask them to make up new phrases or whole sentences. Present a longer narrative with further meaningful examples of the verb. It is worth noting how tightly controlled the release of language is, how carefully the language is selected for difficulty. By limiting the focus in this way, the cognitive demand for students is reduced and they can focus on the key elements being taught.

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